

INTERNATIONAL MIGRATION - A CHALLENGE: A GAIN OR A PROBLEM?

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Abstract

Purpose: *The paper addresses the problems of international migration and the importance of the current labour migration on the Romanian economy. Labour migration is the subject approached by many studies that are the subject of interdisciplinary sciences such as economics, international business, European law, sociology, and many others.*

Methodology/approach: *Due to the evolution of the Romanian economy in recent years, it is important and necessary for any future economist to understand this topic as well as possible.*

Findings: *If the main reason why the labour force has now chosen to leave the country of origin and migrate to economically developed countries is a better living, the aim is to provide children with a better future.*

Research limitations/implications *These results are confirmed by the answers given to the questions formulated in a questionnaire applied in the representative communities.*

Practical implications: *After analysing the statistical data taken from specialized studies, as well as those from the questionnaire, the main question will be answered: "what is international migration - a challenge: a gain or a problem?"*

Originality/value: *Looking ahead, it is necessary to know as much as possible about the factors underlying the development of the country's economy as well as about the factors that determine this labour migration at the international level*

Keywords: *migration, immigration, emigration*

Introduction

The phenomenon of migration has always existed and has materialized since the first appearances of mankind through invasions, transhumance, colonization and crusades, or in general, provoked by the attraction of richer regions about the poorer population.

Although in recent years in some parts of the world also Europe, migration of significant flows, the problem of international migration is for many countries of the world or conjunctural concern, and it is rather to see some developments when creating a movement of people. For the European space, the movement for customers and for a large or important workforce, the enlargement of the EU in successive waves, the demographic aging of the population of (western) European countries at an accelerated and motivating pace, which can be factors in increasing traffic and of labor a labor force.

Nowadays, the demographic population must reappear due to the risks we take care of in the manifestation of crises at local, zonal, continental or global level that influence the social order, or in the triggering of disturbances of ethnic or religious balances.

In terms of population flows, labor circulation may increase in size, but may have a higher intensity and value in number. Globally, migration is relatively low, about 3%¹ of the world's population. Although migration meetings important meetings are in a relatively relative state of the world - no country in the

¹ http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/Migration_and_migrant_population_statistics/ro

world is left out of the flows of international migrants. Currently, the country of origin, country of transit or destination for migrants, but can retain all three attributes listed above, simultaneously.

The current state of research - literature

The specialized literature approaches synthetically and integratively the phenomenon of labor migration² looking for new meanings in approaching the phenomenon of international migration.³

Legal migration must be the result of the common will of the migrant and the receiving Member State, for the benefit of both, and even more so, and for the benefit of the State of origin, in the context of circular migration. In applying the *acquis*, each Member State must decide on the conditions for the admission of migrants into its territory. Romania applies a specific immigration policy, depending on the needs identified at national level, but at the same time concerted, taking into account the impact that this policy may have on other EU countries, while ensuring fair treatment of immigrants and balanced integration in the host company.

Romania is exposed to both legal and illegal migration routes from European countries, but also from eastern and southern countries, having origins in the states of the Middle East, Southeast Asia or Africa. Although in some EU Member States there were migration trends from Central and South American countries, they were not felt in Romania, probably due to the geographical position and low attractiveness for citizens from these states.

Migration is a phenomenon that involves several consequences such as demographic, social, economic and political consequences. The phenomenon has grown significantly since 1980, and the desire to analyze this process has intensified in recent years and has covered all regions of the world, being currently a global problem.

International migration of highly skilled labor is a current feature of labor migration, and is also known as the "brain drain" which clearly evokes a loss of intellectual capital for countries of origin.

Migration is defined as "the mass movement of tribes or populations from one territory to another, determined by economic, social, political or natural factors; migration".⁴ The International Organization for Migration defines the term migration as the process of population movement within a state (internal migration) or across borders (international migration). The phenomenon can also be analyzed, studied from the point of view of their two specific elements: time and space. "Migration involves the territorial relocation of persons between two or more states" the latter being the way of viewing the phenomenon of migration of the United Nations. The two organizations argue in terms of space, that migration is the movement beyond the borders of a country.⁵

In international migration, we encounter two closely related processes: immigration and emigration.

Immigration is defined as the receipt of persons or labor displaced in the country of destination for a temporary or permanent period. The main characteristics of the host country / immigration from the economic point of view are the following: relatively higher degree of economic development; high demand for labor, compared to national availability; low share of the able-bodied population in the total population.

Emigration is defined as having a commute for a person or workforce in terms of residence (country of origin) and country of reception (place of work). Thus, the country of origin is characterized by a lower degree from an economic point of view, with a higher share of youth and, in general, a population with a population activity of the entire population, perhaps high birth rate, but also the absence the possibilities of using them national plan for available labor force, the absence of investigations in some economic sectors. At the same time, the country of origin, for the care of labor or labor problems, there are many countries of emigration.

² Katsel, L.T., Lucas, R.E.B., Xenogiani, Th. – *Effects of Migration on Sending Countries: What Do We Know*, Paris: OECD Development Centre, Working Paper Nr. 250, 2006.

³ Iancu, Nicolae – *Migrația internațională a forțelor de muncă: considerații teoretice și repere economice ale fenomenului migraționist*, București, Editura Pro Universitaria, 2013.

⁴ <https://dexonline.ro/definitie/migra%C8%9Biune>

⁵ <http://www.oim.ro/ro/>

The balance of international migration is represented by the differences between the number of immigrants and the number of emigrants, in reference time (cancellation);

The resident population⁶ includes all persons (Romanian, foreign or stateless citizenship) care and habitual residence in Romania, for a period of at least 12 months.

Types⁷ of migrations encountered so far, even in our country can take into account the country and the country, when the criteria can be established:

- after each number and nature to overcome specific migrations, temporary / seasonal / rhythmic and diurnal;
- according to the residential environment, migrations can be: rural-urban, urban-rural, interurban, intrarural, interurban and intraurban;
- or according to the administrative criterion: internal and external;
- according to the mode of development: organized or unorganized;
- by purpose: economic, tourist, pilgrimage, etc.

Migrations are selective - this gives them a disruptive role; as an exception, they are those organized and carried out according to certain rules. Due to the selective character, the destructuring of the communities takes place, which requires the analysis of the phenomenon by age, by sex, by profession but also by the social environment.

The causes that determine at this moment the international labor migration are based either on the economic conditions in the respective country, or on the general conditions of a political, religious, cultural, ideological, national, geographical or other nature. People leave an area either in search of development opportunities and a better socio-economic level, or take refuge in another area following calamities or disasters, wars, religious or political persecution.

At the macroeconomic level, migration leads to the destabilization of the labor market, by creating either a surplus in certain areas or a labor shortage in certain sectors, for certain periods and in certain areas.

At the microeconomic level, both positive phenomena appear, by increasing the standard of living, satisfaction, the feeling of job security, and negative ones, which aim especially at the relationship with the group of origin.

The impact in Romania means affecting some sectors (construction, services, production) that were facing a shortage of labor, currently alarming unemployment at international and national level, as a result of the crisis that has severely affected various sectors such as construction or banking services. The decline of the active population is also influenced by direct loss and effects over time, due to the imbalance of age structures and as a result of the migration of the young population.

States are concerned with identifying and implementing measures that foreshadow some tendencies to avoid secrecy or to bring it to the lowest level. In Romania in the 1990s, it was based on an asylum application, with employment in the labor market until the asylum application was resolved.⁸ Other ways are: leaving the country with a tourist visa, followed by illegal employment in the destination country, migration mediated by the state and leaving the country of origin by identifying potential employers in the destination country even by the migrant.

The legislative framework

The management of the migration phenomenon is based on the participation of all institutions with competences in this field, through a participatory management and through inter-institutional, national and international cooperation.

The current normative framework that regulates the regime of foreigners in Romania, of the citizens of the EU member states and of the European Economic Area, as well as the legal norms that regulate

⁶ http://www.insse.ro/cms/sites/default/files/com_presa/com_pdf/poprez_ian2017r.pdf

⁷ http://www.insse.ro/cms/sites/default/files/com_presa/com_pdf/poprez_ian2017r.pdf

⁸ https://www.mae.ro/sites/default/files/file/anul_2016/2016_pdf/2016.11.01_anexa_4_oug_194-2002.pdf

asylum in Romania is mainly conferred by GEO no. 194/2002⁹ regarding the aliens' regime in Romania, republished, with subsequent completions, GEO no. 102/2005⁹ regarding the free movement on the Romanian territory of the citizens of the member states of the European Union and of the European Economic Area, approved with modifications and completions by Law no. 260/2005¹⁰, with subsequent amendments and completions, Law no. 122/2006¹¹ on asylum in Romania, with subsequent amendments and completions and GEO no. 56/2007¹² regarding the employment and secondment of foreigners on the Romanian territory, approved with modifications and completions by Law no. 134/2008¹³.

Romania's membership of the EU has led, in recent years, to substantial changes in the legal rules governing the regime of aliens in Romania, the citizens of the Member States of the European Union and the European Economic Area, as well as the legal rules governing asylum in Romania, in order to ensure compliance with European legislation in the field and with other legal instruments of an international nature to which the Romanian state is a party. For the full application of the provisions of the Schengen acquis, since the adoption of the Council decision in this respect, the general framework has been created by adopting legislative, institutional, administrative-technical measures in order to implement the relevant acquis.

The regulation of the migration process is ensured by the International Organization for Migration (IOM). By promoting international cooperation on migration issues, IOM believes that regulated migration benefits migrants and society alike.

IOM opened its office in Romania in 1992 to respond to information and counseling needs related to emigration.

The ILO Constitution¹⁴ provides explicit recognition of the link between migration and economic, social and cultural development, as well as the right of persons to free movement.

1. Method and tools of analysis

In the public administration a lot of data collection methods are used, methods that can be included in the qualitative or quantitative or even mixed ones, this group being formed by the cumulation of the first groups, the most common in this field are: observation, experiment, document analysis, the interview that can be conducted individually or in groups, opinion polling and case study.

In social research, the most common method for the best possible analysis of the migration flows is the opinion poll, by the word opinion can be understood a predisposition or a state towards a certain referent. Beliefs and skills are what form the opinion.

The fundamental aspects that we must take into account when we talk about public opinion are: the intensity of the opinion, the importance of the subject, the establishment of opinions.

It is very important to take into account these three fundamental aspects because if the opinion does not have a desired intensity, and the importance of the subject is very small and the opinions are unstable then it is wrong to take into account the public opinion.

The study has as a basic tool the questionnaire that can be done only when we know exactly how the problem is presented. The questionnaire has an introductory part, a part that aims to gain the trust of the respondent. In this part it is written who makes the questionnaire, for what purpose and for what purpose it can help him. Then follow the questions that must be clear and formulated in accessible language. Mainly short questions are used that can be opened, each to give an answer but there can also be closed questions, which will be answered, yes or no.

⁹ <https://www.politiadefrontiera.ro/files/docu/1460966067379-oug102.pdf>

¹⁰ http://www.cdep.ro/pls/legis/legis_pck.htp_act?ida=59593

¹¹ <https://www.oim.ro/attachments/article/364/LEGEA122ANUL2006.pdf>

¹² http://www.cdep.ro/pls/legis/legis_pck.htp_act?ida=72877

¹³ <http://www.legex.ro/Legea-134-2008-87987.aspx>

¹⁴ <http://www.oim.ro/ro/>

For this study, in addition to the results obtained from the interpretation of the answers received from the application of the questionnaire, statistical data were used from the Eurostat website (statistical office of the European Union) which promotes the following values: respect and trust, promotes innovation and information services.

Research results

The main statistical results show that the population of the European Union in terms of demography and migration is estimated to be growing - 513,154,880 people in 2018 (estimate) compared to 511,698,062 people in 2017. In Fig.1 we see estimated data for 2017: Germany is at the top of the ranking with an estimated total population between 69,400,001 and 83,195,677 people. Next in the ranking are England, France and Italy with the related islands, with a population that is estimated between 55,610,001 and 69,400,000 people.

Between 41,820,001 and 55,610,000 people are only Spain, Poland's population is estimated this year between 28,030,001 and 41,820,000, in terms of Romania, it is located between 14,240,001 and 28,030,000 along with the Netherlands . The rest of the EU28 countries have an estimated population between 443,544 and 14,240,000, these being all the Nordic countries, the Central Western countries (Austria, Hungary, Croatia, etc.) but also the southern countries (Portugal, Greece and Bulgaria).

Fig. 1. EU population in 2017 - demographics, migrants and projections (estimate)

Source: <http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/population-demography-migration-projections/statistics-illustrated>

Although migration is on the rise at EU level, for some Member States the number of migrants is increasing and for others it is declining. Table 1 shows that countries such as Germany, France, Italy, Austria, Romania, Finland and England show a slight increase in emigration, and countries such as Spain and Portugal fall from about 400,430 people, respectively 49,572 people in the year 2014 arrives in 2016 to have emigrants of 327,325 persons, respectively 38,273 persons, even if both countries there is also a decrease in 2015, but this is much smaller compared to 2016. This can be easily seen in fig.2.

Romania in 2014 registered 172,871 emigrants, a value that increased in 2015 by 21,847 people. And compared to 2015 in 2016, it also had an increase of 12,860 people.

Table 1. Emigrant population in the period 2014-2016

Country / Period	2014	2015	2016
Germany	324,221	347,162	533,762
Spain	400,43	343,875	327,325
France	136,328	295,911	157,065
Italy	53,491	146,955	64,428
Austria	49,572	56,689	38,273
Portugal	172,871	40,377	207,578
Romania	15,486	194,718	18,082
Finland	15,486	16,305	18,082
England	319,086	299,183	340,44

Source: <http://appsso.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/nui/submitViewTableAction.do>

Fig. 2. Emigrant population

Source: <http://appsso.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/nui/submitViewTableAction.do>

Immigrant population in the three years analyzed increased considerably

in countries such as Germany, Spain, France, Italy, Austria, Portugal, Romania and Finland, but England recorded decreases if in 2014 the immigrant population was 631,991 people, in 2015 it decreased but by 539 people, but in 2016 they reached 588,993, the difference between 2014 and 2016 it is 42,998 people. I believe that this visible decrease between 2015 and 2016 is also due to the fact that England wants to leave the EU28.

Romania, according to the data in table 2, registered an increase, if in 2014 the immigrant population was 136,035 people, in 2016 it reached 137,455 people, even if in 2015 it had a decrease of 3.24 people. All the above can be seen best in fig. 3, where all the data in table 2 are represented graphically.

Table 2. Immigrant population in the period 2014-2016

Country / Period	2014	2015	2016
Germany	884,893	1,543,848	1,029,852
Spain	305,454	342,114	414,746
France	340,383	364,221	378,115
Italy	277,631	280,078	300,823
Austria	116,262	29,896	129,509
Portugal	19,516	132,795	29,925
Romania	136,035	132,795	137,455
Finland	31,507	28,746	34,905
England	631,991	631,452	588,993

Source: <http://appsso.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/nui/submitViewTableAction.do>

Fig. 3. Immigrant population

Source: <http://appsso.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/nui/submitViewTableAction.do>

The completed questionnaire was applied to a sample of a 125 people who at the time presently works abroad, and has been applied online. The questionnaire included 15 questions, questions that were asked with both open and closed answers. Out of 125 questionnaires, we took into account 105 (represents the number of respondents employed in a paid activity) and 10 (represents the number of employees who do not have a paid activity abroad).

Results of the questionnaire: approximately 33% are between 26 and 35 years old, and the fewest are those over 46 years old only 18%, between 18 years old and 25 years old the percentage is 23% and between 36 years old and 45 years old only 26%. The age at which they went abroad varies between 18 and 45 years and only 16% are those who have chosen to leave at the age of over 46.

Following the centralization of the data, it is observed that the share of females is 33% compared to the share of males, which is 67% of the total number of respondents. This result does not support the fact that men are more willing than women to go abroad to work or that their role in the family is easier to fill, but it results from the fact that hard physical work is the one that requires coverage and can be performed by men. . 55% of the men surveyed are employed in construction (construction sites, stone quarries, wood processing plant), 35% in agriculture and 10% in services (IT, health, transport). 75% of the female population is employed in services (health, housekeeping, including care for the elderly or disabled), 25% in agriculture. Italy ranks first as a destination for females, and Spain as a destination for males; next is Germany (as a choice for women) and England (as a choice for men).

The origin of the respondents is varied: 27% from western Romania, 53% from the east and 10% from the central area of Romania. These weights are not relevant given the number of border crossing points and the fact that, in order to avoid congestion, less frequented crossing points are sought, especially during the holidays (ie those in smaller localities). In addition, due to the introduction of low-cost flights / flights on the main routes connecting Romania with the destination countries for the labor force in our country, this mode of transport is preferred, which offers comfort and time savings.

The results obtained by centralizing the answers, Spain is the main destination of the workforce (27%), followed by Italy (23%), then Germany (20%), France (18%) and the few chose England (12%).). Out of a total of 125 respondents, 87% are legally employed, 11% work occasionally, seasonally and 2% did not want to answer this question. If in the country the field of activity where they worked was in trade / services about 23% after they left, now they work in the field of construction about 24%. The field where

they worked before and registered the lowest value is the field of industry, 8%, and after they left, we find the lowest percentage in the field of health, 11%.

Those who chose to leave previously earned between 1300 lei and 1600 lei, 33%, and in the current moment earns in euro the equivalent of over 4500 lei approximately 80%, and 97% at the moment have the possibility to make savings from the monthly incomes. Even for a lower income, they preferred to go to work abroad in the hope that over time their income will increase and give them real chances for a better life.

Graphic representation of salary income before and after leaving abroad

Unfortunately, most of them, 88% are left alone abroad, leaving the family in the country.

Most are 35% high school graduates, 5% vocational and vocational schools and only 28% are with higher education. Fortunately, 75% would go back, but if certain things changed in the country's leadership. The environment of origin of the respondents is 68% urban and only 32% rural.

Discussions and conclusions

External migration has multiple effects that affect the entire social system. Thus, from this study, we list some levels of their analysis: demographic, social, economic, political, from the perspective of global relations. From the demographic point of view it is clear that if a consistent segment of the active population leaves, then the mortality rate will increase, due to the increase of the older population segment. Also, external migration has a significant influence on the fertility of the country's population. The emigrants increase the fertility rate of the country of destination, reducing the departure of the origin country.

Obviously, the Romanians decide to leave their native country not only because of the level of the net salary. There are other socio-economic factors that determine the decision to emigrate, but the satisfaction with the wage income or the total income obtained is important.

After conducting this study we can find an answer to the question that concerns from economically and socially: international migration - a challenge: a gain or a problem? The results indicate that international labor migration is a short-term gain for the country that provides the workforce but over a long period of time this gain becomes a problem because when the skilled labor force does not return to the country of origin to exercise their skills, the remaining population is aging, thus we will not have a very high yield.

The unemployment rate is rising because of many people give up continuing their studies so they do not have the necessary skills to be able to replace the aging workforce. But for the host country, the one that receives the labor force is a gain for a longer period of time because they will benefit from the apt and well-prepared labor force, but in addition to the gain brought, problems will appear because the population will be more and more. more, the greater the demand for jobs.

Therefore, international migration is currently a challenge not only for the labor force but also for the host country.

Notes

External migration is a strongly conditioned socio-demographic phenomenon. Starting from defining the concept of "migration" and its operationalization in dimensions and indicators, we will analyze the statistical-descriptive which is the impact of the net average wage on the external migration. Then, we will emphasize the influence of external migration on the phenomenon of aging of the population and on the workforce in Romania.

The issue of migration is so complex that it concerns a broad spectrum of specialists in social sciences: demographers, sociologists, geographers, economists, political scientists or experts in international relations. Lately, practicing psychologists and social workers are interested in the social and economic consequences of migration as they must provide services oriented to the needs of migrants faced with problems of socio-cultural integration in the countries of "adoption" or with specific problems of the so-called "return migration". "

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Revue des études sud-est européennes

Institutul de Studii Sud-Est Europene al Academiei Române, colecție.

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